

A STUDY ON EMOTIONAL LITERACY AMONG SECONDARY SCHOOL TEACHERS IN GUNTUR DISTRICT

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Abstract

Emotional literacy is the ability to understand, express and regulate emotions in social contexts. It emphasizes the ability to communicate with certain feeling words in interpersonal relationships. It stands as a bridge between the thoughts and emotions of school stakeholders, contributing to more effective learning, safer schools, and a democratic climate (O'Hara, 2011). It is possible to teach emotions academically, even to make them a part of the curriculum (Antidote, 2003); however, it is essential to also see emotional literacy as a vital skill through the values of the school and the behaviors of teachers. Therefore, it is valuable to evaluate the emotions of teachers in the school environment. The objective of the current research is to find out the emotional literacy of secondary school teachers. In this study, a sample of 100 secondary school teachers from Guntur district in Andhra Pradesh were investigated using a descriptive survey research technique. For the purpose of this study, a standardized tool will be used. Emotional Literacy Skills Scale (ELSS) developed by Melek Alemdar, Hüseyin Anulan (2020). This investigation proposes to determine level of emotional literacy of secondary school teachers and to classify them. To study the effect of the following variables on the emotional literacy of secondary school teachers like gender, locality, school status, teaching experience and marital status.

Key words: Emotional literacy, Secondary school teachers

INTRODUCTION

The quality of education is directly related to the quality of teachers. Due to economic, social, and technological developments, new demands in education have also led to different expectations from the teachers. This has caused drastic changes and transformations in the

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teachers' identity. In the light of scientific and technological developments, it is of course a priority for teachers to adopt novel pedagogies and to support their social and professional development. However, teaching and learning are not just processes of cognition, knowledge, and skill -- they are emotional practices as well (Hargreaves, 2001). Teachers, the mediators of achieving affective goals in society, need to have competencies to recognize, regulate and express their feelings.

Emotional literacy is relevant to school environment because teachers are human resource and play important role in teaching learning process. It is essential to use human resources to make the learning more effective and avoid conflicts among the stallholders, because emotions and feeling which are needed to be properly understood and managed. Emotional literacy helps to create and improve relationships, makes work place environment cooperative and supportive, and develops feeling of community It means to handle emotions in a way that strengthens belief in oneself, enhances personal power build good relationships between individuals and increases performance at workplace.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE: Previous Studies has been observed that **Didem Çetin (2023)** Expresses The Relationship between the Emotional Literacy Skills and Communication Skills of Pre-Service Turkish Teachers. As a result of the study, it was concluded that the levels of the emotional literacy skills and communication skills of the pre-service Turkish teachers are high. The pre-service teachers' emotional literacy skills and communication skills were found to be varying significantly depending on gender in favour of the female pre-service teachers. **Khizar Hayat (2022)** Indicates that Emotional literacy as a predictor of teachers' performance at primary school level in central Punjab. The major findings of the study were there was significant effect of emotional literacy on teachers' performance. The female teachers were better in emotional literacy than male primary schools' teachers. **Ana M. Cristoveo, Adelinda A. Candeias and Jose Lopes Verdasca (2020)** focused that Development of Socio-Emotional and Creative Skills in Primary Education: Teachers' Perceptions about the Gulbenkian XXI School Learning Communities Project. The results show very positive impacts on the professional and personal development of teachers. Teachers reported improvements in student behavior, in the relationships between them and in the classroom environment. **Panel Ekaterina Kliueva , Dina Tsagari (2018)** implies that Emotional literacy in EFL classes: The relationship between teachers' trait emotional intelligence level and the use of emotional literacy strategies. Showed that the level of educational sector (school vs university) plays a significant role in the use of these

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strategies and identified areas for improvement. The results form the basis for recommendations for an EL training program targeting the promotion of EL in the EFL classroom.

NEED AND IMPORTANCE OF THE STUDY: Emotional literacy improves relationships, creates loving possibilities between people, makes co-operative work possible, and facilitates the feeling of community.”(Steiner & Perry, 2003, p.11).

Emotionally competent teachers set the tone of the classroom by establishing supportive and encouraging relationships with their students, coaching in conflict resolutions, encouraging collaborative work among students and acting as a role model for healthy communication and pro-social behavior (Gong et al., 2013). In the spirit of this research, emotional literacy refers to the sum of social, emotional, and behavioral skills that are necessary in all areas of the individual's school, family, and social life (Alemdar, 2022).

According to Kandemir, Dündar and Ozpolat, (2014) the components of emotional literacy are; emotions regulation, motivation, social competences, emotional awareness, and problem-solving. These components of emotional literacy are source of power for a person at work place to perform better. Emotional literacy is the ability to understand, express and regulate emotions in social contexts. It emphasizes the ability to communicate with certain feeling words in interpersonal relationships. however, it is essential to also see emotional literacy as a vital skill through the values of the school and the behaviors of teachers. Emotions are an important component of human life, and therefore each person needs to develop competencies that are related to recognizing and managing emotions, effectively resolving emotional conflicts, and establishing close, positive relationships with other people. Although it can be learned and improved throughout a person’s life. Therefore, it is valuable to evaluate the emotions of teachers in the school environment.

TITLE OF THE STUDY: “A study on emotional literacy among secondary school teachers in Guntur district”.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY:

1. To study the level of emotional literacy of secondary school teachers and to classify them.
2. To find out the influences of the following variables on the emotional literacy of secondary school teachers
 - Gender (Male/ Female)
 - Locality (Rural/ Urban)
 - Type of management (Govt/Private)

- Teaching experience (below 10/above 10)
- Marital status (married /unmarried)

HYPOTHESES OF THE STUDY

The null hypotheses of the study are as follows:

1. The following variables do not make a significant influence on the emotional literacy of secondary school teachers
 - a) Gender (Male/ Female)
 - b) Locality (Rural/ Urban)
 - c) Type of management (Govt/Private)
 - d) Teaching experience (below 10/above 10)
 - e) Marital status (married /unmarried)

METHODOLOGY:

Coverage of the study: It comprises the secondary school teachers working in Tirupati District.

Sampling technique: The sample will be selected following stratified random sampling.

Sampling size: It is proposed 100 secondary school teachers covering all the above mentioned variables

TOOL OF THE STUDY

Emotional literacy scale was developed and Standardized by Melek. Alemdar & Huseyin. Amlann(2020).This scale consists of 31 items in five areas on Motivation (7),Empathy(4),Self-regulation(6),Emotional awareness(6)and Social skills(8).

SCORING PROCEDURE:

Emotional literacy scale was a self reporting five point scale. All these items are given a score from 5 to 1.Those are Almost Always True, Usually True, Often True, Rarely True & Never True. Therefore the higher score on the scale stronger the degree of emotional literacy skill..

DATA ANALYSIS:

OBJECTIVE-1 To study the level of emotional literacy of secondary school teachers and to classify them.

Table 1: The mean, percentage of mean, SD and 1/5th of mean of the total sample of the emotional literacy of secondary school teachers

N	Mean	% of mean	SD	1/5 th of mean
100	34.23	42.79	9.13	6.846

Interpretation: From the above observation as the 1/5th of the mean is less than SD. So that the result is heterogeneous.

Classification of the teachers

It is done on the basis of the level of emotional literacy of the secondary school teachers. This classification is done on the basis of the scores gathered from the secondary school teachers. Totally 31 items the minimum obtained score is 31 and the maximum score is 155. Range of the observations is 125. It is divided into three levels of emotional literacy i.e high, average, low level emotional literacy.

Table: 2 Classification of secondary school teachers on the basis of their level of emotional literacy

Level of emotional literacy	Score scale	No. of teachers	%
Low	30-70	5	5%
Average	71-120	43	43%
High	121-155	52	52%

Interpretation

The teachers are found to be ‘high’ in emotional literacy. It means most of the teachers have high level of emotional literacy skills.

Graph-1: Pie-diagram shows on the levels of Emotional literacy skills

Discussion: Secondary school teachers are found to be high level in their emotional literacy skills. They may manage their professional and personal life in balance to mould the young citizens in their hands.

OBJECTIVE 2: To find out the influences of the following variables on the emotional literacy of secondary school teachers

- Gender (Male/ Female)
- Locality (Rural/ Urban)
- Type of management (Govt/Private)
- Teaching experience (below 10/above 10)
- Marital status (married /unmarried)

Table: 3 Table showing the variable wise distribution Mean, S.D. and t - value for the emotional literacy of secondary school teachers

Sl. No	Variable	Type	N	Mean	S.D	t-value	Status of hypotheses
1	Gender	Male	37	35.73	11.25	0.13NS	Accepted
		Female	63	33.35	7.58		
2	Locality	Rural	53	35.94	8.87	0.02NS	Accepted
		Urban	47	32.30	9.12		
3	Type of management	Govt	52	36.05	8.78	0.018NS	Accepted
		Private	48	32.25	9.18		
4	Teaching experience	Below 10	26	30.35	10.24	0.04NS	Accepted
		Above 10	74	35.09	9.32		
5	Marital status	Married	75	35.09	9.32	0.06NS	Accepted
		Unmarried	25	30.35	10.24		

NS: Not Significant

Table values for 1.98 at 0.05 level and 2.63 at 0.01 level (Garrett, Pg No.461)

Interpretation: There is no significant difference between male and female, rural and urban, Govt and Private, married and unmarried and below 10 years & above 10 years teaching experience of secondary school teachers on their emotional literacy skills.

Discussion and conclusion: Emotional literacy is relevant to school environment because teachers are human resource and play important role in teaching learning process. It is essential to use human resources to make the learning more effective and avoid conflicts

among the stallholders, because emotions and feeling which are needed to be properly understood and managed. It means to handle emotions in a way that strengthens belief in oneself, enhances personal power build good relationships between individuals and increases performance at workplace. It influences various aspects of the teaching and learning process, including student diversity, well-being, teacher self-care, parent-teacher relationships, and long-term student success.

The present study reveals that secondary school teachers are found to be high level in their emotional literacy skills. Respective teacher's emotional literacy under different variables like, gender, locality, type of management, marital status and teaching experience have no significant differences in their emotional literacy and differs in all the above variables. By recognizing the significance of emotional literacy and actively developing these competencies, teachers can create a holistic and nurturing educational experience that benefits their students academically, socially, and emotionally.

Educational Implications:

- Teachers who possess emotional literacy competencies are better equipped to identify signs of emotional distress or challenges faced by their students. They can provide appropriate support, guidance, and resources to help students navigate their emotions and overcome obstacles that may hinder their academic progress.
- By fostering a caring and emotionally supportive classroom environment, teachers contribute to the overall well-being and resilience of their students.
- Another important aspect highlighted by the research is the influence of emotional literacy on teacher self-care and job satisfaction.
- Teachers with high emotional literacy are more aware of their own emotions and are skilled at managing stress, maintaining a positive mindset, and practicing self-care strategies.
- Emotional literacy plays a significant role in promoting positive parent-teacher relationships and parental involvement in education.
- This collaboration enhances the overall educational experience and fosters a sense of shared responsibility between teachers and parents.

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